

2-TOM, 10-SON

SYNTHESIS OF CORROSION INHIBITOR FOR IN 0.5 M HYDROCHLORIC
ACID MEDIUM

Misirov Z.X

zafarmisirov1986@gmail.com

Termez State University of Engineering and Technology.

Abstract.

In this article, the PKA-1 corrosion inhibitor was synthesized based on polyethylenepolyamine and croton aldehyde, its structure was analyzed in YAMR and PMR devices, and its formula was proposed.

Keywords: polyethylene polyamine, croton aldehyde, hydrochloric acid.

Introduction

Corrosion is the destruction of materials, especially metal and metal-based structures, as a result of chemical reactions or electrochemical processes [1]. In general, there are several types of corrosion, which are characterized by the source of origin and properties [2]. In preventing corrosion, the use of corrosion inhibitors can allow us to use structures for a relatively longer period [3]. Hydrochloric acid is widely used in oil and gas extraction. Therefore, in the oil and gas industry, not only corrosion inhibitors for CO₂ and H₂S environments, but also synthesis of corrosion inhibitors with high inhibition efficiency for HCl environments play an important role [4,5].

Experimental part

A chemical compound with the following formula was synthesized in the presence of polyethylene polyamine and croton aldehyde in the presence of dimethylformamide solvent.

It was obtained by mixing the starting materials in a ratio of 1:1 at a temperature of 50 °C for 2 hours. The process was then cooled to room temperature and left for 24 hours.

Table 2.1

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